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THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article describes the forms of public-private partnership, the main directions of economic and social cooperation between the state and business entities, the term "public-private partnership" and its economic essence, the advantages of implementing public-private partnership projects done.*

Key words: *economic functions of the state, private partner, public-private partnership, economic and social projects, "win-win" rule.*

Introduction. Today, when relations between the state and the private sector are increasingly changing from an economic and social point of view, new institutional structures are being formed and their mutual relations are developing.

It is possible to express the processes taking place in two ways: First, the share of income from entrepreneurship in the national income is increasing and the ratio of distribution of added value is changing. Secondly, the obstacles related to the successful implementation of economic and social reforms and the development of private entrepreneurship are decreasing.

It should be noted that as a result of globalization of production and service provision, internationalization of labor markets, increased competition at the level of regions and countries, improvement of mutual cooperation between "state-state", "state-enterprise", "enterprise-enterprise" in society, a new economic relationships are forming.

It is known from the experience of the countries of the world that a specific form of economic relations between the state and private sector has appeared in the economy of a number of countries. Such relations are manifested in the form of public-private partnerships. In this regard, we found it necessary to study and research it in detail.

Research methodology. In the course of the research, the system of economic relations between the state and the private sector, the economic essence and content of the category of "public-private partnership", the implementation of public-private partnership projects, the main forms and main features of public-private partnership in economic fields studying the sodic system and proportions methods such as dialectical, systematic and scientific approach, comparative and comparative analysis were used.

Analysis and results. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public-Private Partnership", public-private partnership is given the following

definition: "Public-private partnership - implementation of a public-private partnership project formalized by a public partner and a private partner for a certain period of time." own resource to increase [9]

Therefore, the idea of transforming the role of the state is based on the modern concepts of managing the economic and social functions of the state:

- coordinating and integrating the interests and resources of the state and the private sector;

- Increasing the participation of various entities with a certain level of influence in the management process. It includes all forms of activity at the community level, taking into account construction projects and regional planning.

Taking into account the above definitions, in our opinion: public-private partnership is a form of implementation of projects in cooperation with the private sector in order to fulfill the tasks and functions of the state in the economic and social spheres, with mutual distribution of responsibilities. In this, the participation of the state partner responsible for the project on behalf of the state, and the private partner on the other hand, is ensured.

In my opinion, the main forms and directions of public-private partnership in our country are as follows:

Figure 1: **The main forms of PPP**

The advantages of PPP for the country's economy are shown in the following:

- availability of opportunities to implement projects of social importance in a short period of time;
- availability of the possibility of use in all sectors and sectors of the economy;
- possibilities of attracting more funds for private financing of state facilities;
- reduction of state expenses for maintenance, repair and operation of highways;
- financing of the construction of state social facilities at the expense of private funds;
- equal distribution of risks between state and private entities;
- Possibilities of introducing modern techniques and technologies in the development of production infrastructure.

The importance of public-private partnership for the country is manifested in the following forms:

- 1) Expansion of opportunities to solve important issues related to the development of the state economy;
- 2) Increasing the efficiency of projects due to the participation of the private sector;
- 3) Strengthening the socio-economic stability of the regions and increasing the level of competition;
- 4) Reduction of rising budget costs due to private financial resources.

Conclusion and recommendations.

Effective and transparent policy, legal and institutional frameworks that encourage private sector participation are critical to the implementation of public-private partnership infrastructure projects. In this regard, legal grounds are being created by our state.

The PPP development agency established under the Ministry of Finance develops the public-private partnership mechanism and projects in coordination with line ministries and agencies, local authorities and other state organizations and state agencies.

There are the following advantages of PPP for entrepreneurs and business circles:

- to support entry into the state sector of the economy;
- Possibilities of getting support from the state;
- on the basis of the "win-win" rule (the benefit of all parties), both the state, entrepreneurs, and ultimately society benefit;
- to have the opportunity to use the experience of foreign countries more widely.

In conclusion, it can be said that the main goal of the public-private partnership structure in Uzbekistan is to create a modern policy and clearly defined legal and institutional frameworks aimed at encouraging the participation of the private sector in Uzbekistan in infrastructure projects.

REFERENCES:

1. Кейнс Дж.М. Общая теория занятости, процента и денег. Пер. с англ. проф. Н.Н.Любимова, под. ред. д.э.н., проф. Л.П.Куракова. – Москва: МИЭМП, 2010.
2. Макконелл К.Р., Брю С.Л. Экономикс. Принципы, проблемы, политика. – М.: Республика, 1992. Т. II. – С. 398.
3. Гэлбрейт, Дж.К. Экономические теории и цели общества / Economics and the Public Purpose (1973) / Под общ. ред. и с предисл. Н. Н. Иноземцева, А. Г. Милейковского. – М.: Прогресс, 1976. – 408 с.
4. Peters J.G, Pierre J. Governance Politics and the State (Political Analysis). – N.Y., 2000.
5. Романова О.А. Теория и практика развития частного государственного партнерства. / Вестник Уральского государственного технического университета. 2007. № 3. С. 41.
6. Джуманиязов У.И. «Давлат-хусусий шерикчилиги асосида корпоратив бошқарувни ривожлантиришнинг айрим назарий-услубий масалалари» / «Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар» илмий электрон журнали. 2017 йил № 3, май-июнь, 9 б.
7. Акбаров, Ф. (2023). Давлат-хусусий шерикликда томонлар ҳамкорлиги. "Science Shine" International scientific journal, 1(1). 15-24 б. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685022>
8. Утемуратова Г.Х. «Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасида давлат-хусусий шерикчилигининг шакллари, моделлари ва механизмлари» / «Иқтисод ва молия» илмий электрон журнали. 2021 йил № 10 (146), май-июнь, 2-12 б.
9. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2019 йил 10 майдаги ЎРҚ-537 сон «Давлат-хусусий шериклик тўғрисида»ги Қонуни. <https://lex.uz/docs/4329270>.
10. Неъматджонович, А. Ф. (2022). Давлат-хусусий шериклик: жаҳон мамлакатлари ва Ўзбекистон тажрибаси. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 2(12), 215-219. <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jars/article/view/4900>
11. Akbarov, G., & Aliboyev, J. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. Eurasian journal of law, finance and applied sciences, 2(13), 125-131. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7461208>
12. Ne'madjonovich, A. G. (2023). Public-Private Partnerships: Experiences of Foreign Countries. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(3), 222-224. <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/synergy/article/view/691>.

13. Боймирзаев, З. М. (2023). Кичик бизнес корхоналарининг экспорт салоҳиятининг ривожлантириш йўналишлари. *О‘zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali*, 2(20), 343-349.
14. Mashrabboyevich, B. Z. (2023). Development of the Export Capacity of Small Business Enterprises in Uzbekistan. *Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(3), 225-228.
15. Boymirzayev, Z. (2023). KORXONALARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISHDA MARKETING TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. "Science Shine" International Scientific Journal, 1(1). <http://science-shine.uz/index.php/ilmnuri/article/view/12>.
16. З.М. Боймирзаев. (2022). Кичик ва ўрта бизнес корхоналарининг экспорт салоҳиятини ошириш. *Архив научных исследований*, 2(1). <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/2161>.
17. Zokirjon, B., & Tursunalievich, A. Z. (2020). Theoretical issues of development of export production of small and medium business enterprises. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(5), 50-58.
18. Боймирзаев, З. М. (2022). Ўзбекистон Республикасининг экспорт салоҳиятини ривожлантиришда кичик бизнес корхоналарининг ўрни. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 1030-1034.
19. Боймирзаев Зокиржон Машраббаевич. (2023). КИЧИК БИЗНЕС КОРХОНАЛАРДА ЭКСПОРТ ТОВАРЛАРИНИ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ҲОС ҲУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *IQRO* , 5(1), 81–86. <https://wordlyknowledge.uz/index.php/iqro/article/view/1940>.
20. Каримова, М. (2022). Хўжалик юритувчи субъектларнинг фаолиятини аудиторлик текширувидан ўтказишда асосий воситаларнинг аудити таҳлили. *Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук*, 2(13), 220-227. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7479077>
21. Dodhomirzaevich, S. S. ., & Nemadjonovich, A. G. . (2024). PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTUAL BASIS. *JOURNAL OF ECONOMY, TOURISM AND SERVICE*, 3(2), 29–34.
22. Karimova, M. (2023). Urgent Issues of Accounting for Fixed Assets in the Context of Modernization of the Country. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(10), 96-100. <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/660>